

Synthesis of Pyridine Alkaloids and Related Compounds. Part—III¹ Synthesis and Local Anaesthetic Activity of Some 2-(1-Hydroxyalkyl)piperidines

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2-(1-Hydroxyalkyl)piperidines (alkyl=*n*-butyl; iso-butyl; *n*-pentyl; iso-pentyl; phenyl and phenethyl) have been synthesised by condensing 2-cyanopyridine with suitable alkyl magnesium halides. The dibenzoyl derivatives of 2-(1-hydroxyalkyl)piperidines have also been synthesised with a view to study their local anaesthetic activities.

THE previous paper² described a new method for the synthesis of coniine and conhydrine in a very good yield. The physiological action of coniine in its various aspects is of great interest and as such has been widely studied. It is well known^{3,4} that the benzoates of the *N*-alkyl derivatives of 2-(β - or γ -hydroxypropyl)piperidines possess local anaesthetic properties. Central nervous system activity of some 2-pyridyl compounds have been studied by Leary, Leary and Slater⁵. The pharmacological actions of pyridine derivatives have been reviewed by Von Oettingen⁶. More recently Fromherz and Spiegelberg^{7,8} have investigated a series of 3-substituted pyridine compounds from a pharmacodynamic view point, and Valenzuela and Huidobro⁹ have studied the effects of some similar compounds upon neuromuscular transmission. No study on 2-substituted piperidine compounds relating to the anaesthetic properties discussed presently has been described so far.

It, therefore, appears that the synthesis of coniine, conhydrine and some other hemlock alkaloids, their homologues and analogues with a view to a

systematic study of their physiological properties may prove of great value.

The previous method² has been extended to the synthesis of related compounds with side chains at position 2 of the pyridine and piperidine nuclei. Thus the present work contains part of a research project, aiming at the preparation of a number of pyridine and piperidine compounds with a view to study their anaesthetic properties.

2-Cyanopyridine¹⁰ on condensation with appropriate alkylmagnesium halides afforded the corresponding 2-acylpyridines. 2-Acylpyridines, when subjected to catalytic hydrogenation over freshly reduced Adam's catalyst in the presence of glacial acetic acid in each case, absorbed 4 moles of hydrogen and produced the corresponding 2-(1-hydroxyalkyl)piperidines (Table 1). Thus it is clear that the carbonyl group and pyridine nucleus were hydrogenated simultaneously. The products lacked IR carbonyl absorption and showed a broad band of OH group between 3280-3290 cm⁻¹. The UV

TABLE 1—2-(1-HYDROXYALKYL)PIPERIDINES

Alkyl group	M.P.*	Yield (%)	Formula		% of C	% of H	% of N	λ_{\max} (m μ)	ϵ_{\max}	$\nu(\text{O-H})$ cm ⁻¹
<i>n</i> -Butyl	100-101°	57	C ₉ H ₁₉ NO	Found :	68.72	12.20	8.90	223	2140	3290
				Reqd. :	68.74	12.18	8.91	260	1170	
iso-Butyl	118-119°	50	C ₉ H ₁₉ NO	Found :	68.70	11.98	8.89	221	2120	3280
				Reqd. :	68.74	12.18	8.91	259	1130	
<i>n</i> -Pentyl	80-81°	80	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ NO.H ₂ O	Found :	63.41	12.32	7.39	224	4450	3285
				Reqd. :	63.45	12.25	7.40	262	2380	
iso-Pentyl	108-109°	62	C ₁₀ H ₂₁ NO.H ₂ O	Found :	63.43	12.31	7.40	227	4520	3280
				Reqd. :	63.45	12.25	7.40	266	2410	
Phenyl	172-173°	70	C ₁₃ H ₁₇ NO	Found :	75.33	8.87	7.41	223	4480	3290
				Reqd. :	75.35	8.96	7.32	262	2380	
Phenethyl	198-199°	50	C ₁₅ H ₁₉ NO	Found :	76.13	9.41	6.81	220	1290	3285
				Reqd. :	76.05	9.33	6.82	260	6160	

*Shining colourless leaflets from ether.

TABLE 2—NO-DIBENZOYL DERIVATIVES OF 2-(1-HYDROXYALKYL)PIPERIDINES

Alkyl group	M.P.	Formula		% of C	% of H	% of N	Duration of local anaesthesia in minutes
<i>n</i> -Butyl	116-118°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	Found :	75.55	7.50	3.73	1.5
			Reqd. :	75.59	7.45	3.80	
iso-Butyl	130-131°	C ₂₃ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	Found :	75.43	7.61	3.79	2.0
			Reqd. :	75.59	7.45	3.80	
<i>n</i> -Pentyl	101-105°	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₃ N	Found :	75.93	7.49	3.68	1.5
			Reqd. :	75.96	7.70	3.70	
iso-Pentyl	122-123°	C ₂₄ H ₂₉ O ₃ N.H ₂ O	Found :	72.49	7.69	3.51	2.0
			Reqd. :	72.51	7.86	3.52	
Phenyl	114-115°	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ O ₃ N	Found :	78.43	6.33	3.50	2.3
			Reqd. :	78.17	6.31	3.51	
Phenethyl	143-144°	C ₂₇ H ₂₇ O ₃ N	Found :	78.41	6.60	3.38	2.0
			Reqd. :	78.42	6.58	3.39	

Procaine—4

spectra showed two maxima of much lower intensity (220-227) and (259-266 m μ). The corresponding NO-dibenzoyl derivatives were also prepared (Table 2).

Pharmacological Report :

A preliminary report on pharmacological properties is summarised in Table 2. The local anaesthetic activities of NO-dibenzoyl derivatives of 2-(1-hydroxyalkyl)piperidines were determined by application of 1% solution of benzoates in ethyl alcohol to a rabbit's eye and noting the duration (in minutes) of the anaesthesia produced (Table 2). Procaine was used as the standard compound for comparison. It may be seen from the data that the duration of local anaesthesia in nos. 1 and 3 is too short but nos. 2, 4, 5 and 6 have nearly the same duration of anaesthesia. Because of the short duration of anaesthetic activities of these compounds in comparison to procaine, they show little promise of anaesthetic application at present and could not be considered as good local anaesthetics.

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected and were determined in pyrex capillaries. The infrared spectra were determined on Perkin-Elmer Infracord, Model 237 and Unicam S.P.200. Mulling agent used was spectroscopic KBr. Ultraviolet absorption measurements were made with a Unicam S.P.800.

2-Acylpyridines : 2-*n*-Butyrylpyridine :

2-Cyanopyridine (5 g) in dry ether (35 ml) was gradually added during 10 minutes to a well cooled and stirred solution of Grignard's reagent prepared from magnesium (1.4 g), one small crystal of iodine and *n*-propylbromide (7.25 g) in dry ether (35 ml). The reaction mixture was refluxed with stirring for 3 hours, cooled in ice bath and then decomposed by dropwise addition of cold water (5 ml), followed by dilute sulphuric acid (5*N*; 60 ml). The aqueous layer was separated and the ethereal layer was extracted twice with dilute H₂SO₄ solution (2*N*; 2 × 30 ml). The combined acid extracts were mixed together and heated on water bath for 15' minutes,

cooled in ice and then made strongly alkaline with saturated sodium carbonate solution. The oil which separated was extracted with chloroform and dried (Na₂SO₄). The chloroform was removed and the residue (6.15 g) on distillation gave a straw coloured liquid (5.5 g; 75%), b.p. 100°/2 mm.

Other 2-acylpyridines were also prepared by applying the same method. They gave the corresponding picrates and 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones.

2-(1-Hydroxyalkyl)piperidines : 2-(1-Hydroxy-*n*-butyl)piperidine :

2-*n*-Butyrylpyridine (2 g) in glacial acetic acid (25 ml) was catalytically reduced over freshly reduced Adam's catalyst (60 mg) during 29 hours at 25°/759.5 mm. The total uptake of hydrogen was 1360 c.c. (about 4 moles). The reaction mixture was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated into a small volume under reduced pressure on water bath. It was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide solution (10%) and extracted with ether. The distillation of the dried (Na₂SO₄) extract gave a solid residue, m.p. 96-97°, which on repeated crystallisation from ether gave colourless shining leaflets (1.2 g; 57%), m.p. 100-101°.

Other 2-(1-hydroxyalkyl)piperidines were also synthesised in the similar manner (Table 1). The NO-dibenzoyl derivatives are listed in Table 2.

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References

1. K. B. PRASAD, H. A. N. JALLO and K. S. AL-DULAIMI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1969, 2134.
2. K. B. PRASAD and S. G. SHAW, *Chem. Ber.*, 1965, 98, 2822.

3. W. H. HUNT and R. J. FOSBINDER, *Anaesthesiology*, 1940, **1**, 305.
4. C. W. TULLOCK and S. W. MCELVAIN, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 961.
5. J. F. O. LEARY, D. E. LEARY and I. H. SLATER. *Proc. Soc. Expt. Biol. med.*, 1951, **76**, 738.
6. W. F. VON ORTINGEN, *The Therapeutic Agents of the Pyrrrole and Pyridine Compounds*, Edwards Brothers, Inc. Publishers, Ann. Arbor, Mich., 1936.
7. K. FROMHERZ, *Schweiz. Med. Wochensh.*, 1949, **79**, 521.
8. K. FROMHERZ and H. SPIEGELBERG, *Helv. Physiol. Acta.*, 1948, **6**, 42.
9. F. VALENZUELA and F. HUIDOBRO, *J. Pharmacol.*, 1948, **92**, 1.
10. E. FRELEY and E. M. BRAVERS, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.* 1959, **81**, 4004.